

CLINICAL ASSESSMENT OF POTENTIAL ROLE OF CHITOSAN IN THE MANAGEMENT OF PERIODONTITIS PATIENTS

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Abstract

Aim: The use of chitosan gel may be considered as a new local chemotherapeutic material for treatment of chronic periodontitis patients. This study was aimed to evaluate clinical effects of 1 % chitosan gel in the treatment of chronic periodontitis patients. **Materials and Methods:** 30 patients were divided into two groups. Group I: consisted of 15 sides received scaling and root planing with intrapocket application of chitosan gel. Control Group: consisted of 15 sides received scaling and root planing only. All patients were subjected to initial phase therapy and instructed for plaque control regimen. Then. Evaluated clinically at baseline, 3 and 6 months after treatment. The data were collected, tabulated and statistically analyzed by SPSS (Statistical Package for Social sciences). **Results:** The clinical parameters such as probing depth. Clinical attachment level were recorded at baseline at 3 and 6 months _ In all groups, statistically significant differences were showed in both groups at the different intervals when compared to the baseline. Probing depth show a statistical significant difference in group I when compared with group II at 3 months and no difference at 6 months. The Clinical attachment level show a statistical significant difference in group I when compared with group II at 3 and statistical significant difference in group I When compared with group II at 6 months. **Conclusions:** Intrapocket application of chitosan gel 1 % appeared to be effective adjunctive in treatment of stage II to III chronic periodontitis.

1. INTRODUCTION

Periodontitis is defined as a chronic inflammatory disease of the oral cavity caused by bacterial biofilm attached to tooth surfaces, which cause destruction of the periodontal tissues by the interaction of periodontopathogenic microorganisms and the host's immune response, where the periodontal pathogenic microorganisms trigger the disease process [1].

The main aim of periodontal therapy is to improve the gingival health of the patient and preserve the remaining periodontal tissues. Both local factors, as well as the bacterial load of periodontopathogens, require reduction along with the correction of behavioral

factors such as cessation of smoking and tobacco consumption is a part of periodontal treatment [2].

Chitosan is a cationic polysaccharide that occurs naturally or can be obtained by deacetylation of chitin. Its linear structure consists of Beta-1, 4O-glycosylamine. The active regions of chitosan include amino and amide groups in C-2 location and hydroxyl groups in C-3 and C-6.

The deacetylation results in enzymatic hydrolysis which transforms chitosan into a water-soluble and low-molecular-weight oligosaccharide. Chitosan is soluble in dilute acid medium and forms a cationic polymer. The biocompatibility of this material with high viscosity and high water-binding capacity makes it suitable for use in different forms such as gels, chips, and membranes [3].

Additionally, chitosan is a hydrophilic polysaccharide which has a wide range of bio-dental applications with its antimicrobial, immunostimulatory, hemostatic, and wound-healing properties. In pediatric dentistry, chitosan is used to prevent the mucoadhesion of cariogenic bacteria [4]. It is used along with chewing gum and mouthwash owing to its antibacterial and antiplaque effects [5].

The antimicrobial activity of chitosan would prevent any possible infections. The functional groups present in chitosan derivatives are quaternary ammoniumyl, guanidinyll, carboxyalkyl, hydroxyalkyl, thiolcontaining groups, and hydrophobic groups such as long alkyl chains and substituted phenyl and benzyl rings [6].

It was believed that amino groups of chitosan in contact with physiological fluids are protonated. Chitosan binds with anionic groups of microorganisms and causes agglutination of microbial cells and inhibition of their growth.

Additionally, the antimicrobial activity of chitosan is directly related to the absorption of polysaccharide to the bacterium and this causes alterations in the cell wall structure and increases the permeability of the cell membrane, causing cell death. Additionally, chitosan also interferes with bacterial coaggregation [7].

It has been conducted that chitosan containing formulations remain for a prolonged time on the application site; its tissue regeneration ability and hemostatic properties eliminate any additional material necessity, such as barrier membranes and bone grafts in regenerative therapies. Chitosan also shows osteoconductivity and induction of neovascularization, which leads to accelerated bone growth [8].

Researchers evaluated chitosan's biodegradability and biocompatibility properties, making it suitable for application as a biomaterial and scaffold for hard tissue regeneration. Chitosan with its chemical H-bond chains, cross-linkings, and NH₂⁺ with negative tissues in the human body thus provides good stability to start new bone cell formation at an early stage of bone healing. It was proved that spongy chitosan supports the proliferation of osteoblasts, can increase osteogenesis, and helps in guided bone regeneration [9].

It was found that Chitosan affects specific cells involved in the process of wound healing and stimulates macrophages to release IL-1 that stimulates fibroblast proliferation ^[10].

In other studies, it was revealed that chitosan concentration of 3% could offer a base for an optimum modulation in drug dose and make them efficient to use as a local drug delivery agent.

Moreover, the local drug delivery system using chlorhexidine with chitosan base polymer reported a reduction in probing depths and gain in clinical attachment levels and concluded that chitosan loaded drugs can be an alternative treatment modality for patients with chronic periodontitis in recall intervals ^[11].

Moreover, Chitosan is used in a range of drug delivery applications from oral drug delivery to systemic therapy for a variety of uses including insulin, anticancer drugs, and gene delivery ^[12].

The aim of present work was to assess the potential role of chitosan in the management of periodontitis patients.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Patient Selection:

The present study included 30 patients with stage II to III periodontitis. Patients were randomly assigned into two groups. Subjects were selected from the outpatient clinic, Oral Medicine and Periodontology Department, Faculty of Dentistry. Screening of patients was continued until the target parameters was achieved. This study was approved by the ethics committee of the scientific research Faculty of Dentistry following Helniski declaration.

All Patients involved in this study signed a written consent and fully agreed to participate in this work.

2.2 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria:

A) Inclusion Criteria:

Patients were selected to be systemically free according to the modified Cornell Medical Index.

Patients having stage II to III periodontitis with probing pocket depths ≥ 5 mm, interdental CAL 3-4mm to ≥ 5 mm ^[13].

B) Exclusion criteria:

Patients received antibiotic, anti-inflammatory, and periodontal procedure within the previous 6 months preceding the study. Smokers patients.

Participants complying with the inclusion criteria were randomly assigned using a computer-generated list of random numbers ^[14].

2.3 Preparation of Materials:

Chitosan was purchased with low molecular weight (50.000 to 100.000 u) and degree of de-acetylation (DD 75 %).

- 1) The chitosan is dissolved in an acetic acid solution (pH = 4). The prepared solution is injected drop by drop using a syringe in agelling solution (solution of sodium hydroxide 3M or sodium dodecylsulphate solution 50mM). The obtained solution is maintained for 6 hours at room temperature (25°C).
- 2) Obtained hydrogel (in the form of balls) is filtered, then immersed in baths containing ethanol/water solutions. One obtains finally an alcogel, which thereafter undergoes an evaporative drying or a drying with supercritical CO₂ to finally obtain 1% concentration.
- 3) Following the conventional periodontal treatment (scaling and root planing), intrapocket application of 1% chitosan gel was done to the patients of the first group (study group).

2.4 Study Groups:

The Patients were divided equally into two groups as follows:

- **Group I -n=15 (Chitosan hydrogel):**

The periodontal pockets ≥ 5 mm were isolated. Chitosan hydrogel were prepared in the same steps that mentioned before in the methodology and then the prepared gel was applied to the site of defect with the deepest probing pocket measurement twice per week for one month^[15]. Periodontal dressing (Coe-pack) was to secure the hydrogel in place.

- **Group II -n=15 (Control group):**

In the control group, patients were treated with scaling and root planning only and full periodontal charts were obtained.

2.5 Clinical Parameters Assessment

The following clinical parameters were evaluated for every patient included in the study at baseline, 3, and 6 months after treatment:

- Periodontal probing depth (PD) according to Glavind and Löe (1967)^[16].
- Clinical attachment level (CAL)^[17].

2.6 Statistical Analysis

All assessed parameters were statistically analyzed with SPSS-16 statistical software. First data will all data were presented as mean and standard deviation. Student t-test was used evaluate difference between the two groups. One-way analysis of variances (ANOVA) was used to analyze the data for several groups. P-value was considered significant when $P \leq 0.05$.

3. RESULTS

The present study included 30 patients stage II to III periodontitis. Patients were randomly assigned into two equal groups.

The periodontal health status of all patients included in this study was assessed with criteria of PD, CAL at baseline, three and six months respectively. The data of all examined subjects included in the present study were recorded, tabulated, and subjected to statistical analysis where values were presented as mean and SD values.

3.1 Probing Depth (PD) Measurement

By comparing the PD at baseline (0 months) between the treated and control group it was revealed that the difference in PD was statistically significant for groups G1(at base line) , G2 (3 months), with P-value of 0.01 , 0.05 respectively. (Tables 1, 2 and 5). (Fig 1).

Table 1: PD for Chitosan and Control Group

Groups	$\bar{X} \pm SD$	Maximum	Minimum
G1 – baseline	5.12 ± 0.68	7	5
G1 – 3 month	3.21 ± 0.58	5	3
G1 – 6 month	4.93 ± 0.58	5	3
G2 -baseline	5.31 ± 0.63	7	5
G2 – 3 month	2.98 ± 0.63	5	3
G2 – 6 month	3.37 ± 0.58	5	3

X: Mean, SD: Standard deviation.

Table 2: Comparisons PD between Chitosan and Control Group

		PD					
		$\bar{X} \pm SD$					
	G1 baseline	G1 3 month	G1 6 month	G2 baseline	G2 3 month	G2 6 month	
	5.12 ± 0.68	3.21 ± 0.58	4.93 ± 0.58	5.31 ± 0.63	2.98 ± 0.63	3.37 ± 0.587	
	13.3	6.7	8.3	9.3	12.3	13	F-Value
	0.01	0.028	0.014	0.001	0.05	0.07	P-Value
Multiple Comparisons							
	MD	95% CI				Pvalue	Significance
		Lower bound		Upper bound			
G1 baseline	5.8	5.59		6.24		0.01	HS
G1 3 month	3.8	3.64		4.19		0.028	S
G1 6 month	3.9	3.22		3.78		0.014	S
G2 baseline	5.8	5.54		6.13		0.001	HS
G2 3 month	0.5	3.54		4.13		0.05	S
G2 6 month	0.1	3.31		3.59		0.07	NS

X: Mean, SD: Standard deviation, P value: probability, Value S: Significant, NS: Non significant, CI: Confidence interval, **HS, (P<0.01), S*: Significant(P<0.05), NS: not significant (p>0.05), superscript letters indicate a statistically significant difference within the same column, while; same letters indicate no statistically significant.

Figure 1: PD of Chitosan and Control Group

3.2 Clinical attachment loss (CAL) measurement

Comparison of CAL at baseline between the chitosan and control group reported that the difference was statistically significant for groups G1 baseline, G2 (3 months) with P-value of 0.01, 0.05 respectively. **Table (3,4 and 5), Fig. (2).**

Table 3: CAL for Chitosan and Control Group

Groups	$\bar{X} \pm SD$	Maximum	Minimum
G1 – baseline	5.12 ± 0.68	7	5
G1 – 3 month	3.21 ± 0.58	5	3
G1 – 6 month	4.93 ± 0.58	5	3
G2 -baseline	5.31 ± 0.63	7	5
G2 – 3 month	2.98 ± 0.63	5	3
G2 – 6 month	3.37 ± 0.58	5	3

X: Mean, SD: Standard deviation

Table 4: Comparison of CAL between Chitosan and Control Group

		PD						
		$\bar{X} \pm SD$						
		G1 baseline	G1 3 month	G1 6 month	G2 baseline	G2 3 month	G2 6 month	
		5.12 ± 0.68	3.21 ± 0.58	4.93 ± 0.58	5.31 ± 0.63	2.98 ± 0.63	3.37 ± 0.587	
		13.3	6.7	8.3	9.3	12.3	13	F-Value
		0.01	0.028	0.014	0.001	0.05	0.07	P-Value
Multiple Comparisons								
	M	95% CI				Pvalue	Significance	
	D	Lower bound	Upper bound					
G1 baseline	5.8	5.59	6.24		0.01	HS		

G1 3 month	3.8	3.64	4.19	0.028	S
G1 6 month	3.9	3.22	3.78	0.014	S
G2 baseline	5.8	5.54	6.13	0.001	HS
G2 3 month	0.5	3.54	4.13	0.05	S
G2 6 month	0.1	3.31	3.59	0.07	NS

X: Mean, SD: Standard deviation, P value: probability, Value S: Significant, NS: Non significant, CI: Confidence interval, **HS, (P<0.01), S*: Significant (P<0.05), NS: not significant (p>0.05), superscript letters indicate a statistically significant difference within the same column, while; same letters indicate no statistically significant.

Figure 2: CAL of Chitosan and Control Group

Table 5: Significance Comparisons of PD and CAL between chitosan & control group

$\bar{X} \pm SD$		Significance
G2 baseline	G1 baseline	HS
G2 baseline	G1 - 3 months	S
G2 baseline	G1 - 6 months	S
G2 baseline	G2 - 3 months	HS
G2 baseline	G2 - 6 months	HS

4. DISCUSSION

In the present investigation chronic periodontitis patients were selected because this condition is considered as one of the most common bacterial infection worldwide with prevalence in mild to moderate forms ranging from 13% to 57% in different populations depending on oral hygiene and socio-economic status^[18].

The primary goals of the periodontal therapy are to preserve the natural dentition, to maintain and improve periodontal health, comfort, esthetics and function. As regard to the conventional strategies for treatment of chronic periodontitis by effective plaque

control and calculus removal as well as regular follow-up combines with oral hygiene instruction can significantly enhance the clinical parameters and reduce the clinical signs of inflammation. About 20%—30% of all chronic periodontitis cases do not respond favorably to conventional periodontal treatment. Many factors may contribute to that response, such as improper removal of bacterial deposits and calculus, poor plaque control, systemic conditions leading to an impaired immune response, defective restorations, occlusal dysfunction, periodontal-endodontic involvement and others. In these cases, other treatment approaches may be required [19].

Application of local drug delivery as adjunctive to scaling and root planing provide a sustained release of short doses of the drug over a long period of time without need to dose repeatedly unlike systemic antibiotics and sub gingival irrigation [20].

In addition, it was reported that, the use of these local delivery drugs reduce probing depth, sub gingival microflora and clinical signs of inflammation [21-22]. The present study aimed to use a new modality in the periodontal therapy by intrapocket application of chitosan gel 1% as adjunctive to the basic conventional therapy to overcome the unresponsive cases treated by conventional periodontal therapy alone. Because of its ability in impairing the colonization of the tooth surface by *Streptococcus mutans*, chitosan has been shown to be potential in minor quantities in toothpastes, mouth-rinses, or chewing gum [23].

In addition, it possesses bioactive properties including wound healing, antimicrobial, tissue regeneration, and hemostatic activities [24].

In the present study the probing pocket depth measurement showed a statically significant difference in group I and group II at 3 months when compared to baseline, while there was no statically significant difference in group I when compared with group II at 6 months. These results are in accordance to the findings of Akncbay H (2007). However, the mean difference of probing pocket depth in group I when compared with group II at 3 months was statistically significant. These results are contrary to the findings of Akncbay H (2007) [25] who recorded that statistically significant difference between two groups at 3 and 6 months. This may be attributed to the difference of number and frequency of application of chitosan according to Akncbay H, injection repeated twice weekly for 6 months, but in this study injection was repeated twice weekly for one month. Reduction in PPD is a beneficial clinical outcome used to assess the success of periodontal therapy, it can be conjectured that the anti-bacterial properties of chitosan aided in decreasing the PPD.

The gain in clinical attachment level at 6 months showed statistically significant difference in group I and group II statistically in compared to baseline. In addition, the gain in clinical attachment was statically significant greater in group I when compared to group II at 3 months and statistically significant at 6 months. These results in contrary to study of Akncbay H (2007) who showed no significant gain in clinical attachment level in chitosan treated patients. Chitosan is a bioadhesive and the reduction in PD values and the gain in clinical attachment level could be the result of the attachment on the root surfaces

which could be allowed by chitosan because of its supportive and organizing effect on the histological architecture of the gingiva. However, the type of the attachment after chitosan application and soft tissue healing should have defined with histological investigations in future studies ^[26].

5. CONCLUSION

Intrapocket application of chitosan gel 1% appeared to be attractive and effective adjunctive in treatment of stage II to III chronic periodontitis.

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